

CSIRO Workshop on Electronic Structure Computations and Theoretical Methods for Materials Sciences, Minerals and Industry

8-9 JULY 1998

**CSIRO Molecular Science
Bayview Avenue
Clayton, Victoria 3169, Australia**

Workshop Handbook

CSIRO Workshop on Electronic Structure Computations and Theoretical Methods for Materials Sciences, Minerals and Industry

Aim of the workshop:

The aim of the workshop is to bring together a small (as it is) group of computational and theoretical physicists working in Australian Universities and a group of CSIRO scientists working in general areas of Minerals, Materials Sciences, Molecular Sciences, etc. We would like to provide a tutorial exposition of the most recent developments in the theory and computations to experimental scientists from CSIRO and also provide opportunity to

experimentalists and practically oriented researchers to talk about problems they work on. This meeting should give us all an opportunity to create new relationships between the Academia and CSIRO and also establish more contacts in the small community of electronic structure specialist in Australia. We would also like to solicit ideas and suggestions regarding the most desirable, suitable and affordable software for CSIRO problems to be installed on NEC SX-4.

Microfacet A

Sponsors:

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High Performance Computing and
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Organising Committee:

Dr Stephen Fletcher, CSIRO Minerals
Mr Ian Harrowfield, CSIRO Minerals
Dr Alf Uhlherr, CSIRO Molecular Sciences
Dr Marek Michalewicz, CSIRO, Mathematical and Information Sciences, HPCCC

Programme Committee:

Dr Mukunda P. Das, ANU

Dr Marek Michalewicz, CSIRO, Mathematical and Information Sciences, HPCCC

The list of speakers:

Dr Mukunda P. Das, ANU

Density functional approach: a standard model for low energy physics

A/Prof. John Dobson, Griffith U.

Density Functional Theory of Many-Electron Systems

Dr U. Faul, Research School of Earth Sciences, ANU

Structure and properties of grain boundaries

Dr Stephen Fletcher, CSIRO Minerals

Some opportunities for molecular simulation in mineral processing

Dr Frederic Green, CSIRO Telecommunications and Industrial Physics

Current noise as a probe of electronic structure

Ian Harrowfield, C MacRae, N Scarlett, N Wilson, CSIRO Minerals

X-ray and Electron Microcharacterisation of Minerals and Materials

Dr Ian Jackson, Research School of Earth Sciences, ANU

Oxide and silicate minerals at high P and T: Thermodynamical behavior and physical properties

Dr Anatoli Kheifets, ANU

Calculation of energy-momentum distribution of electrons in solids and electron momentum spectroscopy of crystalline and disordered materials

Dr Michael Ling, Monash University

Computational Materials Science: from Schroedinger equation to alloy design

Dr Marek Michalewicz, CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences, HPCCC

How to deal with defects? Electronic structure methods for non-perfect materials

Dr Andrew Smith, Monash U.

Plasmons. When are they observed? How can they be calculated?

Dr Brian Smith, CSIRO Molecular Sciences

Methods for Accurate Energies

A/Prof. Phil V. Smith, U. of Newcastle

Lattice dynamical and electronic structure calculations on clean and chemisorbed semiconductor surfaces

Prof Ian Snook, RMIT

The use of computer simulation methods to investigate materials structure and crystallisation

Dr Billy Todd, CSIRO Molecular Science

Indefinite-time molecular dynamics simulations of elongational flow

Dr Feng Wang, U. of Melbourne

Electronic structural investigation of excited and ionized species: An introduction to MOLPRO

Dr Dave Winkler, CSIRO Molecular Sciences

'Orbital Imaging' of Strained Organic Molecules using Density Functional Theory and Electron Momentum Spectroscopy

Dr Alf Uhlherr, CSIRO Molecular Sciences

Computational Polymer Science: a Game of Mix'n Match

Dr Ling Zhang, CSIRO Minerals

Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Silicate Melts

WEDNESDAY, 8 July 1998		THURSDAY, 9 July 1998	
			Session 4, <i>Chair: John Dobson, Griffith University</i>
		9:00 - 9:30	Some opportunities for molecular simulation in mineral processing <i>Stephen Fletcher</i> <i>CSIRO Minerals</i>
		9:30 - 10:00	Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Silicate Melts <i>Ling Zhang</i> <i>CSIRO Minerals</i>
10:00 - 10:45	Registration <i>Coffee</i>	10:00 - 10:30	How to deal with defects? Electronic structure methods for non-perfect materials <i>Marek Michalewicz</i> <i>CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences, HPCCC</i>
	Session 1, <i>Chair: Marek Michalewicz, CSIRO</i>	10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break
10:45 - 11:00	Opening: <i>Dr Rod Hill, Chief, CSIRO Minerals</i>		Session 5, <i>Chair: John Dobson, Griffith University</i>
11:00 - 11:45	Density functional approach: a standard model for low energy physics <i>Mukunda P. Das</i> <i>ANU</i>	11:00 - 11:30	X-ray and Electron Microcharacterisation of Minerals and Materials <i>Ian Harrowfield, C MacRae, N Scarlett, N Wilson</i> <i>CSIRO Minerals</i>
11:45 - 12:15	Density Functional Theory of Many-Electron Systems <i>John Dobson</i> <i>Griffith University</i>	11:30 - 12:00	Oxide and silicate minerals at high P and T: Thermodynamical behavior and physical properties <i>Ian Jackson</i> <i>Research School of Earth Sciences, ANU</i>
12:15 - 12:45	Methods for Accurate Energies <i>Brian Smith</i> <i>CSIRO Molecular Sciences</i>	12:00 - 12:30	Structure and properties of grain boundaries <i>Ulrich Faul</i> <i>Research School of Earth Sciences</i> <i>ANU Lunch Break</i>
12:45 - 13:45	Lunch Break	12:30 - 13:30	Lunch Break
	Session 2, <i>Chair: Stephen Fletcher, CSIRO</i>		Session 6, <i>Chair: Mukunda Das, ANU</i>

13:45 - 14:15	Electronic structural investigation of excited and ionized species: An introduction to MOLPRO <i>Feng Wang</i> <i>University of Melbourne</i>	13:30 - 14:00	Computational Materials Science: from Schroedinger equation to alloy design <i>Michael Ling</i> <i>Monash University</i>
14:15 - 14:45	Current noise as a probe of electronic structure <i>Frederic Green</i> <i>CSIRO Telecommunications and Industrial Physics</i>	14:00 - 14:30	'Orbital Imaging' of Strained Organic Molecules using Density Functional Theory and Electron Momentum Spectroscopy <i>Dave Winkler</i> <i>CSIRO Molecular Sciences</i>
14:45 - 15:15	Plasmons. When are they observed? How can they be calculated? <i>Andrew Smith</i> <i>Monash University</i>	14:30 - 15:00	Calculation of energy-momentum distribution of electrons in solids and electron momentum spectroscopy of crystalline and disordered materials <i>Anatoli Kheifets</i> <i>ANU</i>
15:15 - 15:45	Coffee Break	15:00 - 15:30	Lattice dynamical and electronic structure calculations on clean and chemisorbed semiconductor surfaces <i>Phil V. Smith</i> <i>University of Newcastle</i>
	Session 3, <i>Chair: Stephen Fletcher, CSIRO</i>	15:30 - 15:50	Closing Remarks
15:45 - 16:15	The use of computer simulation methods to investigate materials structure and crystallisation <i>Ian Snook</i> <i>RMIT</i>		
16:15 - 16:45	Computational Polymer Science: a Game of Mix'n Match <i>Alf Uhlherr</i> <i>CSIRO Molecular Sciences</i>		
16:45 - 17:15	Indefinite-time molecular dynamics simulations of elongational flow <i>Billy Todd</i> <i>CSIRO Molecular Sciences</i>		
17:15 - 18:00	POSTER SESSION		
18:00 for 18:15	Informal dinner at the Monash University Club		

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Current Noise as a probe of electronic structure

F. Green

GaAs IC Prototyping Facility Program
CSIRO Telecommunications and Industrial Physics
PO Box 76, Epping NSW 2121

Abstract:

In metals and semiconductors, microscopic carrier fluctuations are directly measurable in terms of thermal and shot noise. Under "nonstandard" conditions, be it at high fields or at mesoscopic dimensions, fluctuations carry important information on electron dynamics. Such information is otherwise out of reach to conventional transport studies. I illustrate this with several examples: nonequilibrium thermal noise in nonparabolic conduction bands, shot noise in narrow mesoscopic wires, and the optimal design of quantum wells for low noise in heterojunction transistors.

Plasmons. When are they observed? How can they be calculated?

Andrew E. Smith

Department of Physics
Monash University
Clayton, Victoria

Abstract:

Plasmon excitation dominates energy loss processes for all charged particles with excitation energies above several electron volts. This is because the Coulomb force is long range and the plasmon is a delocalised collective oscillation of the conduction electrons. In turn plasmons provide a basis for a wide range of experimental spectroscopies. Recent work has been carried out to establish the first principles properties of plasmons beginning with the electronic band structure [1]. As an example, results for Si have been computed for the plasmon contribution to the inelastic (absorption) scattering potential, that is central to quantitative electron microscopy [2].

- [1] T.W. Josefsson and A.E. Smith, Phys. Rev. B 50 7322 (1994).
A.J. Forsyth, T.W. Josefsson and A.E. Smith, Phys. Rev. B 54 14355 (1996).
- [2] A.J. Forsyth, A.E. Smith and T.W. Josefsson, Acta Cryst. A 53 523 (1997).
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ABSTRACTS

Density Functional Theory: A Standard Model for Low Energy Physics

Mukunda P. Das

Department of Theoretical Physics, RSPHysSE
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The Australian National University
Canberra, ACT 0200, Australia
Email: Mukunda.Das@anu.edu.au

Abstract:

Physics of many interacting particles is notoriously difficult. A major attraction of the density functional theory (DFT)[1] is that it facilitates approximate calculations on many-body systems without requiring the construction of many-body wavefunctions or their equivalent. Instead one extracts the needed information from a one-body quantity, the number density. In the recent years DFT has been successfully applied to a variety of physical systems. In this talk we shall discuss the foundation of the theory, two commonly used approximate functionals (local density and generalised gradient approximations) and analyse a large number of examples of ground state properties. We compare results of local and nonlocal calculations in relation to experiments and conclude on the status of the theory in terms of chemical accuracy.

[1] See for recent developments, *Electronic Density Functional Theory*,
Ed. J.F.Dobson, G.Vignale and M. P. Das, Plenum Press (1998).

Density Functional Theory of Many-Electron Systems

John F. Dobson

School of Science
Griffith University, Nathan, Queensland 4111

Abstract:

Density Functional Theory (DFT) is a powerful tool in the study of diverse interacting many-body systems. Here we will discuss its application to groundstate energetics and structure of many-electron systems. We will also discuss electronic excitation energies.

Groundstate density functional theory is rigorous, but requires approximation to permit practical calculations. The local density approximation (LDA) was for years the only practical method for ab-initio prediction of groundstate properties of systems of very many electrons. LDA calculations are fast but only moderately accurate. In the case of small systems for which many-body wavefunction methods are workable, the LDA is certainly inferior to them.

The status of DFT changed with the emergence of successful generalized gradient approximations (GGAs). For small-to-medium systems, the new GGAs can sometimes rival the accuracy of traditional many-body methods while consuming vastly less computer time. For larger systems GGAs are the only serious contenders for groundstate energetics. GGAs have revolutionized the field of quantum chemistry, though troublesome areas remain.

Groundstate DFT cannot justifiably be used for electronically excited states. We will briefly describe the relatively new field of time-dependent density functional theory which does not have this in-principle limitation.

We will also briefly describe new highly nonlocal density functionals capable of treating long-ranged "van der Waals" correlations which are missed by the LDA and GGA.

Methods for Accurate Energies

Brian J. Smith

Biomolecular Research Institute
Royal Parade
Parkville, VIC 3052

Abstract:

There have emerged over the past decade a growing number of model chemistries which aim at achieving estimates of molecular energies to a target accuracy of ± 10 kJ/mol. These include the many variations of Gaussian-2 theory and the CBS methods. Several examples of the application of these methods will be presented, including calculation of proton affinities, heats of formation, ionization energies, and the energetics of radical cyclization reactions. Particular emphasis will be placed on the performance of alternative methods, including density functional theory, in relation to these high-level methods.

Electronic Structural Investigation of Excited and Ionized Species: An Introduction to MOLPRO

Feng Wang and Frank P. Larkins

School of Chemistry
The University of Melbourne
Parkville, Victoria 3052, Australia

Abstract:

The recently available MOLPRO package is a complete system of ab initio programs for molecular electronic structure calculations. As distinct from many other commonly used quantum chemistry packages, its emphasis is on highly accurate computations of molecules, with extensive treatment of electron correlation through the multiconfiguration-reference CI, coupled cluster and associated methods. It has made MOLPRO a very useful tool to be capable of electronic structure calculations for excited or ionized states of molecules. It uses a powerful internally contracted CI method and sophisticated optimization method, that is, the algorithm in the CI coefficient changes is quadratically convergent. For simple cases, convergence is usually achieved in 2-3 iterations. As a result, MOLPRO is able to significantly reduce the computational costs with a negligible loss of accuracy. Some examples on accurate electronic structure calculations of excited and ionized molecular species are demonstrated.

Current Noise as a probe of electronic structure

F. Green

GaAs IC Prototyping Facility Program
CSIRO Telecommunications and Industrial Physics
PO Box 76, Epping NSW 2121

Abstract:

In metals and semiconductors, microscopic carrier fluctuations are directly measurable in terms of thermal and shot noise. Under "nonstandard" conditions, be it at high fields or at mesoscopic dimensions, fluctuations carry important information on electron dynamics. Such information is otherwise out of reach to conventional transport studies. I illustrate this with several examples: nonequilibrium thermal noise in nonparabolic conduction bands, shot noise in narrow mesoscopic wires, and the optimal design of quantum wells for low noise in heterojunction transistors.

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Abstract:

Plasmon excitation dominates energy loss processes for all charged particles with excitation energies above several electron volts. This is because the Coulomb force is long range and the plasmon is a delocalised collective oscillation of the conduction electrons. In turn plasmons provide a basis for a wide range of experimental spectroscopies. Recent work has been carried out to establish the first principles properties of plasmons beginning with the electronic band structure [1]. As an example, results for Si have been computed for the plasmon contribution to the inelastic (absorption) scattering potential, that is central to quantitative electron microscopy [2].

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A.J. Forsyth, A.E. Smith and T.W. Josefsson. Phys. Rev. B 6400 (1997).

The use of computer simulation methods to investigate materials structure and crystallisation

Ian Snook

Department of Applied Physics
RMIT
Melbourne

Abstract:

Computer simulation techniques e.g. the Monte Carlo (MC) and Molecular Dynamics (MD) methods have a long history of being used to investigate the properties of matter in bulk and at surfaces but mainly in the equilibrium or the steady state and often for either liquids or crystalline solids. Unfortunately, many interesting structures and processes don't fall into these areas, for example, many fascinating solids are not crystalline and processes such as nucleation and crystallisation are not in a steady state. Here, I will discuss two of our attempts to overcome these limitations in particular cases. The first problem of investigating the structure of a non-crystalline solid may be tackled by the Reverse Monte Carlo (RMC) process. Here I will discuss some of our recent work on using the RMC method to obtain models for the structure of glassy carbon and amorphous carbon from experimental data. An example of the second problem is the study of nucleation and crystallisation. I will discuss some of our recent work in this area for Lennard-Jones systems and show what we have learnt by the use of large scale (10,000's to 100,000's atom) MD simulations.

Computational Polymer Science: a Game of Mix'n Match

Dr Alf Uhlherr

CSIRO Molecular Science
Bayview Avenue
CLAYTON VIC 3169

Abstract:

The properties of polymeric materials (plastics, composites, gels, coatings etc) can be varied dramatically by changes in chemical composition and molecular architecture. In some ways this makes them ideal candidates for "rational design" by computational methods. However such studies must also recognise the extraordinary complexity of behaviour that these materials exhibit over a wide range of length and time scales. This talk briefly addresses some examples of how we selectively apply many different computational methods to appropriate industrial problems. These applications include aerospace composites, biomaterials, food packaging, security devices, detergents and explosives. The talk will also highlight the need for new simulation techniques - currently under development - which will most likely form the backbone of polymeric materials design over the next decade.

Indefinite-time molecular dynamics simulations of extensional flows

Billy Todd

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Abstract:

Nonequilibrium molecular dynamics (NEMD) has been growing in popularity and usefulness over the past decade. In particular, its application for studying the rheological behaviour of chain molecules has provided insight into the cooperative dynamics of molecular fluids under conditions of shear. Sadly, its application to fluids undergoing extensional flows - of great importance to the polymer processing industry - has been hampered by serious technical limitations placed upon the overall size of the simulation cell. In short, an isochoric fluid under extension must contract in at least one of the cartesian dimensions. This in turn implies that a simulation will have a finite lifetime, ceasing once the length of the simulation cell in the contracting dimension reaches its minimum of twice the range of the interaction potential radius. If, as is generally the case for molecular fluids under extension, the maximum time of the simulation is less than the relaxation time of the fluid, then a nonequilibrium steady-state is unachievable, thus limiting the usefulness of the rheological information available.

In this talk we show how it is possible to simulate one important type of extensional flow, namely planar elongational flow, by application of the periodic boundary conditions devised by Kraynik and Reinelt [Int. J. Multiphase. Flow 1, 1045 (1992)]. They are remarkable in that they ensure that the system is both spatially and temporally periodic for indefinite simulation times, thus guaranteeing the fluid will attain a nonequilibrium steady-state. The application of these periodic boundary conditions represents the most promising method yet devised for simulating polymer melts under elongation.

Some Opportunities for Molecular Simulation in Mineral Processing

Stephen Fletcher

Senior Scientist
Electrochemistry and Electrometallurgical Processing
CSIRO Minerals
Clayton, Victoria

Abstract:

CSIRO Minerals has recently invested in hardware and software for molecular simulation and molecular graphics. Our goal is to improve the efficiency of various key steps in mineral processing, and to provide a molecular imaging system for enhanced visualization of solids and surfaces. In the present talk I will describe some of the (non-confidential) problems presently confronting researchers in Minerals, and explore some possible modes of solution.

Molecular Dynamics simulation of silicate melts

Dr Ling Zhang

G K Williams CRC for Extractive Metallurgy
CSIRO Minerals
Box 312, Clayton South, Victoria 3169

Abstract:

Molecular modelling and simulations using empirical potential, i.e., force field approach have been widely used in studying structural, dynamic, surface and interfacial properties. Since the success of molecular dynamics (MD) simulation of silica by using the Born-Mayer-Huggins pair potential by Woodcock et al [1] in the middle 70's, there have been many attempts of MD simulation of silicates in the form of crystals, glasses and melts. The force fields used are from pair to three-body and shell-core to try to improve the accuracy of the calculated structural properties. These studies together with experimental techniques, such as XRD, Raman and NMR have contributed to our advanced understanding on the structure of silicate glass and melts in recent years. In the past few years MD simulations of silicate melts have been carried out to study the properties of slag (molten silicates) at CSIRO minerals. One frequently encountered problem is the availability and the reliability of the force field used for the simulations.

This is due to

(1) the force field parameters for some common elements in minerals and metallurgical melts may not be available, and

(2) the available force field parameters in the current form may not adequately describe some effects, such as polarization of the ions and crystal field effect for transition metals.

It is hopeful that the quantum mechanical approach would assist the development of improved force field, both in the choice of the functional form and in obtaining consistent force parameters.

References

[1] L. V. Woodcock, C. A. Angell and P. Cheeseman, J. Chem. Phys. 65, (1976), p.1565.

How to deal with defects? Electronic structure methods for non-perfect materials

Marek Michalewicz

CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences
Joint Bureau of Meteorology / CSIRO HPCCC
24th Floor, 150 Lonsdale Street, Melbourne, Victoria 3000

Abstract:

Two approaches developed to study electronic structure of disordered solids are: the recursion method and the equation-of-motion method. I will briefly introduce the recursion method, the more commonly used; and then I will present my own experiences with the equation-of-motion method. Example of applications will include the studies of 3D and 2D samples, surfaces, surface defects such as microfacets, and atomic steps, and also point defects (oxygen vacancies) in TiO₂.

I will also present our recent results on extremely fast implementation of the equation-of-motion method on the NEC SX-4 supercomputer. The program can be applied to non-periodic, disordered nanocrystalline samples, metals, transition metal oxides and other systems.

It scales linearly, $O(N)$, runs with a speed of up to 43 GFLOPS/s on NEC SX-4 vector-parallel supercomputer with 32 processors and computes electronic densities of states for multi-million atom samples in mere minutes.

The largest test computation performed was for the TiO₂ sample consisting of 7,623,000 atoms. Mathematically, this is equivalent to obtaining a spectrum (electronic density of states DOS) of an $n \times n$ Hermitian operator (Hamiltonian) where $n = 38,115,000$. We will discuss practical implications of being able to perform electronic structure computations of this great speed and scale.

X-ray and Electron Microcharacterisation of Minerals and Materials

I Harrowfield, C MacRae, N Scarlett, N Wilson

CSIRO Minerals, Clayton, Victoria

Abstract:

Micron-scale, analytical spatial resolution and the facility to map the supra-micron texture of sectioned assemblages sustain electron probe microanalysis (epma) as the most widely-used technique in minerals and materials microanalysis but microstructural information must be obtained by electron diffraction. However, the supra-micron texture is usually lost in preparing thin samples for transmission microscopy.

We show that it is possible to extend the mapping capability of epma to include structure-related data derived by X-ray spectroscopy. X-ray peak shape sensitivity to structure can be considered using quantum chemical software which enables the computation of densities of states (DOS) of emitter atoms. Because large beam currents are needed, electron beam damage to specimens during spectroscopy of peak shapes must always be borne in mind and, where possible, checked by X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy, a technique which is likely to be more widely used in minerals analysis with the development of X-ray focusing techniques.

Oxide and silicate minerals at high pressure and temperature: thermodynamic behaviour and physical properties

Ian Jackson

Research School of Earth Sciences
Australian National University
Canberra ACT 0200, Australia

Abstract:

A brief exposition of the interests of the Petrophysics Research Group in RSES in the chemical and physical behaviour of oxide and silicate materials under the extreme P-T conditions of the Earth's deep interior. The inaccessibility of these conditions to direct experimental study places a premium on indirect experimental methods such as the study of structural analogues stable at lower pressures, and on guidance by theory.

Particular interests which will be highlighted include

- * the relative stabilities of alternative high-pressure crystalline polymorphs and the thermodynamics of solid-state phase transitions and melting;
- * thermoelastic properties of high-pressure oxide and silicate polymorphs, including compressibility, elastic moduli, phonon dispersion (e.g. soft modes), and thermal expansivity;
- * diffusivities of atomic species and their implications for mechanical behaviour;
- * electronic structure and electrical conductivity of transition metal oxides e.g., FeO in rocksalt (B1) and NiAs (B8) polymorphs.

Structure and Properties of Grain boundaries

Dr. Ulrich Faul

Research School of Earth Sciences
The Australian National University
Canberra ACT 0200, Australia
email: uli.faul@anu.edu.au

Abstract:

Grain boundaries modify single crystal properties of materials by interrupting the regularity of the crystal lattice. Grain boundaries therefore can have considerable influence on bulk properties of polycrystalline materials. A new technique, electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) allows the determination of a large number of grain orientations and relative orientations of neighbouring grains in fine-grained materials. In magnesium-silicate ceramics with an added melt fraction the melt seems to act as a filter for grain boundary energies by wetting some grain boundaries but not others. The observed relative orientations of pairs of grains however can not be described by models treating the grain boundaries from a geometrical point of view, i.e. without considering the actual atom positions at the interface. A better understanding of grain boundary structures in ceramic materials might be achieved if it would be possible to theoretically determine the atom positions and energies at grain boundaries relative to grain interiors.

Computational Materials Science: from Schroedinger equation to alloy design

Michael F. Ling

Department of Physics
Monash University
Clayton, Victoria 3168

Abstract:

Over the past decade or so, computational materials science research based on electronic structure theory has matured to the stage that many ground state properties of alloys can be reliably calculated. With the advent of supercomputers, alloys of industrial importance can now be designed and their physical properties predicted before expensive and time consuming experimental tests are carried out. In this talk, some recent developments will be discussed and the power and the advantage of computational materials science research illustrated.

Lattice dynamical and electronic structure calculations on clean and chemisorbed semiconductor surfaces

A.J.Dyson, Jian-Zhong Que, M.W.Radny, P.V.Smith and Sanwu Wang

Physics Department
University of Newcastle
Callaghan, NSW, 2308

Abstract:

All of the work of the Newcastle Surface Theory Group is focussed on studying the geometrical and electronic structure of clean and chemisorbed semiconductor surfaces. This is achieved by employing a number of different theoretical techniques. These include:

- (i) Geometry optimisation by minimising the total energy of a representative cluster of atoms using either the semi-empirical or ab initio Hartree-Fock (HF)/Density Functional Theory (DFT) methods contained within the Gaussian94 software package.
- (ii) Calculation of the charge density distributions, local density of state and COOP functions using the output from Gaussian94 cluster calculations.
- (iii) Geometry optimisation and determination of the electronic structure using a periodic slab representation and the Berlin first-principles plane wave code (fhi96md).
- (iv) Empirical molecular dynamics simulations at different temperatures and exposures employing either clusters or slabs.

Use of these various techniques will be illustrated by applications to the following systems:

- (i) The chemisorption of B, Al and H on the Si(111) $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ R30 $^\circ$ surface.
- (ii) The dimer reconstructed Si(001) surface.
- (iii) The interaction of atomic hydrogen with the Si(111)7x7 surface.
- (iv) The chemisorption of C₂H₂, CH₃ and H on the Si(001)2x1 surface.

'Orbital Imaging' of Strained Organic Molecules using Density Functional Theory and Electron Momentum Spectroscopy

**D. A. Winkler(1), W. Adcock(2), M. J. Brunger(2), I. E., McCarthy(2),
M. T. Michalewicz(3) and W. von Niessen(4)**

(1) CSIRO Molecular Science, Private Bag 10, Clayton South MDC, Clayton 3169

(2) Departments of Chemistry and Physics, Flinders University of South Australia
G.P.O. Box 2100, Adelaide, SA 5001

(3) CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences, HPCCC
24th Floor, 150 Lonsdale Street, Melbourne, 3000

(4) Institute für Physikalische and Theoretische Chemie, Technische Universität
D-38106, Braunschweig, Germany

Abstract:

Electron momentum spectroscopy (EMS) studies of the valence shells of [1.1.1]propellane, 1,3-butadiene, ethylene oxide and cubane is reviewed. Binding energy spectra were measured in the energy regime of 3.5–46.5 eV over a range of different target electron momenta, so that momentum distributions (MDs) could be determined for each ion state. Each experimental electron momentum distribution is compared with those calculated in the plane wave impulse approximation (PWIA) using both a triple-z plus polarization level SCF wave function and a further range basis sets as calculated using density functional theory. Electron correlation effects are an important factor in describing the chemically sensitive outer spatial (low momentum) regions of the HOMO electron densities, making the use of DFT methods attractive.

A critical comparison between the experimental and theoretical momentum distributions allows us to determine the optimum wave function for each molecule from the basis sets we studied. As EMS is most sensitive to these outer valence electrons of molecules, it provides a sensitive method of optimizing DFT wavefunctions. These wave functions then allow us to investigate chemically or biologically significant properties of these molecules. EMS-DFT also shows promise in elucidating the character of molecular orbitals and the hybridization state of atoms.

Calculation of energy-momentum distribution of electrons in solids and electron momentum spectroscopy of crystalline and disordered materials

A. S. Khelifets

Research School of Physical Sciences and E.
Australian National University
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Abstract:

We determine, both experimentally and theoretically, the energy-momentum distribution of valence electrons in crystalline and disordered solids. This allows us to map the electron density in momentum space which is complementary to conventional electron charge density in coordinate space. Important ground state properties of solids can be elucidated by using this approach.

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